

THE DIFFERENCE BETWEEN FOLK TALES AND LITERARY TALES

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Jumanyozova Muhabbat

Urganch State University Faculty of Pedagogy

Associate Professor of the Department of

"Primary Education" Methodology:

Ozodova Zulfiya is the daughter of Gayrat

Student of Urganch State University

Аннотация.

В данной научной статье говорится об общем понятии народной сказки и литературной сказки и их различии.

Ключевые слова.

сказка, литературная сказка, народные сказки, фольклор, сказитель.

Literary and folk tales belong to the same genre, so it is quite difficult to determine how a folk tale differs from a literary tale. Only the form and internal content of the story have visible differences. The basis of the plot of any fairy tale is a wonderful story about the unprecedented adventures (sometimes accidents) of the main characters, but in folklore works the plot is built according to a traditional scheme, but in a literary story it is the author's version of the presentation.

Folk tales

To determine the difference between literary and folk tales, you need to study the definition of these concepts. A folk tale is an ancient cultural heritage, which, even in a decorated form, preserved the imagination of the ancestors about the relationship between the surrounding world (nature) and man. Here the bright features of human society, national identity, faith and lifestyle are manifested, where the border between good and evil is clearly defined, the basic laws and moral principles of morality are reflected. Tales called folk tales have their own classification:

- Magic ("Magic Ring", "Two Cold", "Cold").
- Epic ("Bulat is a good man", "Vavila and the buffoons", "Dobrynya and the snake").
- Household ("Poor Master and Servant", "Thieves and the Judge", "Expensive Dinner").

- Heroes ("Ivan - the son of a farmer and the miracle - Yudo", "Ivan - the son of a cow", "Nikita Kozhemyaka").

- Satirical ("Good pop", "Fool and birch", "Porridge from an ax").

In the presented classification, a special place is occupied by animals ("goose-swans", "goat-window", "machete and bear"). Experts associate their appearance with ancient pagan traditions and beliefs.

Literary tales

When comparing folk and literary tales, remember that the latter appeared much later than the former. By introducing educational ideas into European literature, readings of the first author in the 18th century - reworking of folk legends and traditional fantastic plots in the 19th century... Among the most successful in this field are A. Hoffman, C. Perrot, G. H. Andersen and, of course, the Brothers Grimm - there are well-known classics of the genre.

The similarity of literary and folk tales is determined by the fact that both of them repeat folklore motifs and have magical attributes, but the choice of main characters in the literary development of the plot is strictly subject to the will of the author. . Also, the literary tales of the second half of the XIX century become very close to short stories and even stories. An excellent example can be the works of Russian writers: L. Tolstoy and A. Pogorelsky, Europeans: S. Lagerlef and L. Carol.

When comparing the characteristics of a folk and literary fairy tale, special attention should be paid to the folklore traditions of the author's fairy tale, which unites it with the folk:

- Writers use folklore plot motifs in their works (moral and moral temptation - the test of the main character, the presence of animal helpers, the miraculous origin of the heroes, the stepmother's hatred of her stepdaughter, etc.).

- According to the respected Russian folklorist V. Ja Propp, writers use traditional, familiar from childhood images of central characters who perform certain functions (antagonist, hero, sidekick of the main character, donor, prankster, stolen object , a false hero).

- In their creations, storytellers create time and space in accordance with the unwritten laws of the fairy-tale folklore world: this place is imaginary, and sometimes eternal: a distant kingdom, a ruined well, etc.

- Use of poetic speech techniques: three repetitions, continuous epithets, oral formulas, folk language, proverbs and sayings, phraseological units. Such close attention to folklore sources allows us to see the appeal of the storytellers and the specific characteristics of the literary tale.

Differences

To understand how a folk tale differs from a literary tale, it is necessary to pay attention to the uniqueness of the form and content, in particular:

- In the author's fairy tale, the image is more vividly expressed, that is, the appearance, emotions, actions and scenes of the characters are described in more detail, in detail and, most importantly, colorfully.

- IN the literary fairy tale there is a deeper and more detailed study of psychologism, the inner world, feelings and emotions of the characters.

- The heroes of the author's myth are not generalized types, but have their own individual character, for example, writers such as Ershov, Pushkin, Odoevsky pay attention to the psychological motives of the actions and actions of the heroes.

- Like any literary work, fairy tales of writers are distinguished by their stable stability, which determines its emotional tonality. For example: "The Tale of Tsar Saltan..." - pure, light, noble; "The story about the dead princess and the seven heroes" - beautiful, gentle, sad; "The tale about the priest and his worker Balda" - joking, teasing; "The tale about the fisherman and the fish" - sarcastic, but sad.

What is the difference between a folk tale and a literary tale? The author's work shows the reader the author's face, the main difference between folklore, which reflects the spiritual world, ideals and ideals of this ethnic group, and the personality of a certain narrator is erased.

So, what is the difference between a folk tale and a literary tale? The second, the author's work, unlike the first, arose as a result of collective creativity as an epic subtype. Literary myth is a well-established genre of fiction, and folklore is a specific type of folklore genre that is characterized by oral retelling.

Literary fairy tales are one of the most respected literary genres in children. Even the program includes works of writers such as school reading S. Pushkin, V.F. Odoevsky, P.P. Ershova, V.A. Zhukovsky included in the Golden Fund of Children's and Russian Literature. Their reading contributes to the early formation of children's moral and aesthetic ideas, develops their literary horizons and general culture... But most importantly, such works contribute to the development of creativity, imagination and unconventionality of a young student. thinking

Due to the specific nature of oral creativity, there is a close connection between folklore and literature, which reflects a person's perception of the world around him and the laws of its development. public conscience... However, folklore and literary works have fundamental differences that determine their features and characteristics.

Folklore in the broadest sense is a historically established, inculcated folk tradition, an oral or collective co-authored game form, a poetic summation of the experience of many generations. Folklore genres include ritual, song and epic. To epic genres include fairy tales, legends, epics, legends, fairy tales, as well as sub-types of oral folk art - proverbs, sayings, riddles and anecdotes. The word "folklore" is often used in a narrow sense - to define the content and method of creating oral artistic images characteristic of these genres.

The beginning is a folk epic associated with the development of literature as an art form in many cultures... It served as the basis for chronicles and biographies of saints; the principle of storytelling taken from folk tales was used in the construction of adventure and fantasy novels, which are the prototypes of many genres. modern prose; figurative structure and rhythmic organization of epics, historical and ritual songs are reflected in the author's poetry.

But literary works did not obey the laws of folklore, had a more complex composition, an arbitrary plot, and could exist only in written form, because each of them was an original work created by one person.

Since the Renaissance, the characteristic feature of fiction becomes the style of the author, and the object of the image is the inner world of the hero, in which the reader finds the moral priorities and characteristics of the era that are characteristic of a certain era. historical period in the development of society.

The modern literary process is a complex multifaceted cultural phenomenon, which has already been formed and is manifested in new forms of oral creativity. Unlike literature, folklore preserves its stable forms and the compositional structure of the text. The inner world of the hero is closed: only the event or behavior is important, it shows not the characteristic features, but the principles of behavior that are the basis of the order that establishes the balance between good and evil.

Summary

Folklore is a special form of oral folk art, which expresses generalized ideas about the structure of the world and human society in oral images. Literature as an art form is written and reflects the inner world of a person in the system of social relations that have developed in a certain historical period. Folklore works are the result of a collective creative process, in which copyright cannot be established. Literary authorship combines works that are reliably known. Folklore genres are subject to strict rules for creating a plot, creating an image system, and choosing the means of artistic expression... The principles of plot creation and image creation in literary works are determined by the author.

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